

THE USE OF ADAPTIVE LEARNING MATERIALS TO ENHANCE DEPED SCIENCE TEACHERS' AND STUDENTS' PERFORMANCES

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The Use of Adaptive Learning Materials to Enhance DepEd Science Teachers' and Students' Performances

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Abstract

The availability, adequacy and relevance of instructional materials in the classroom can influence quality teaching, which can have a positive effect on the students' learning and academic performances as well as the teachers' performances. In this study, the teaching performance of the DepEd science teachers in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) were identified and their relationships were determined. The pre-test and post-test performances of the science students under ALMs and ADMs and their mean gain scores were determined. The problems encountered by the teachers and perceptions of students in using ALMs and ADMs were identified. Using prescribed questionnaires and pre and post-test, 30 science teachers, 5 school heads, and 60 science students from two selected sections were evaluated. The results showed that the use of ALMs and ADMs in teaching science subject were both effective in enhancing teaching performances as rated by their head teachers, peers and students. The teachers' performances under ALMs and ADMs have a significant difference (t -value=2.18, t -value=2.72, Tabular=1.76, Tabular=1.69) based on the head teachers and peers' ratings while they have no significant difference (t -value=-1.407, Tabular=1.69) based on the students' ratings. The student's pre-test improved after introducing both ALMs and ADMs and there is a significant difference in the mean gain score under ALMs and ADMs (t -value=3.099, Tabular=1.672). Thus, the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) increases DepEd science teachers' and students' performances in teaching and learning science subject.

Keywords: *adaptive, learning, materials, performance*

Introduction

Instructional materials are powerful tools for enhancing teaching and learning. Their effectiveness for being beneficial to learners is mostly decided both their quality and adequacy. As an outcome, adequacy and relevancy affect teaching quality, which benefits students positively associated with academic success. These instructional materials are utilized to assure that the topic is successfully delivered; as a result, they must be creative, educational, and even adaptable enough to be updated or changed.

Textual learning materials are employed in the teaching and learning process as alternatives to traditional materials. They are important since they point out the greatest approaches for students to learn. They also provide clarification on the complex concepts being taught to the students. Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) as well as Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are two of them.

Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) are non-traditional education programs recognized by Department of Education (DepEd) that employ a dynamic learning approach and a curricular delivering program that incorporates non-formal and informal sources of information and skills. This can involve using facilitator-assisted and participatory self-instructional printed or audio-based learning materials, video cassettes, face-to-face organized learning group, semi-structured and unstructured talks, one-on-one sessions, group study and self-learning groups, demonstrations sessions, home visits, mentorship, and remediation.

In order to accomplish Education for All (EFA), the Philippine educational system enhanced its Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) through 2011. This Alternative Delivery Mode of Instruction was developed to help underprivileged students and students on the verge of dropping out improve their academic performance and overcome economic and social obstacles to education (Department of Education, 2011; Philippines ADMs Evaluation Philippines, 2012). This provided more important and suitable learning opportunities for elementary students. The introduction of Alternative Delivery Modes into Philippine Educational System, on the other hand, makes it more difficult for certain students to meet the national standards outlined in the materials, leading to poor performance. Furthermore, because ADMs were not permitted to conduct traditional face-to-face classes even during COVID-19 pandemic, classes were moved to home-based learning.

Home-based learning occurs online using online education and learning. However, due to poor and unpredictable internet connections, shifting to online teaching and learning can be challenging in some areas, specifically in the BARMM's remote areas. As a result, as part of its Education Continuity Plan, the MBHTE-BARMM used Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) including alternate modes of learning.

Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are written materials that were not designed for teaching but have a sufficient level of difficulty to be employed in a classroom setting. These Adaptive Learning Materials tools originally designed in Bangsamoro for Bangsamoro learners. They offer individualized learning that seeks to engage each student by providing efficient, effective, and personalized learning paths. The Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) set the following characteristics for these ALMs: easy, simple, activity-based, engaging, cost-effective; use materials found at houses; strengthen family relations; start encouraging

coordination and interaction; should relate to real - life setting; and, home-based learning (Talicop, 2020). Thus, the Adaptive Learning Materials' (ALMs) effectiveness in enhancing the MBHTE BARMM's DepEd science teachers and students' performances is the focus of this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the effectiveness of Adaptive Learning Materials in enhancing performances of DepEd science teachers and students. Specifically, it answered to the following questions:

1. What is the teaching performance of the DepEd science teachers in using:
 - 1.1. Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs); and,
 - 1.2. Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?
2. What are the pre-test and post-test performances of the science students under:
 - 2.1. Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs); and,
 - 2.2. Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mean gain scores between the students under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and under the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performances between the teachers under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and under the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?
5. What are the problems encountered by the teachers under the:
 - 5.1. Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs); and,
 - 5.2. Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?
6. What are the perceptions of students in using:
 - 6.1. Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs); and,
 - 6.2. Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the quasi experimental and descriptive survey designs. The students were divided into two groups: the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) Control group and the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) Experimental group. Each of these two groups was consist of 30 students. The total of 60 students was chosen from a pool of 120 students. The average pretest scores from the test were used to determine the selection. A random selection technique was used to create each cluster. At the end of the teaching-learning process, both groups were given a Post-Test to determine their learning gains. In addition, Grade 6 Science students, 30 instructors, and the 5 school's heads were given a survey questionnaire to rate teachers' performance, problems most encountered by the teachers and perceptions of students towards the use of ALMs and ADMs methods of science teaching-learning.

Respondents

The study was conducted on the third quarter of the School Year 2021-2022 at Dapiawan Central Elementary School, located at the Barangay Dapiawan, Datu Saudi Ampatuan, Maguindanao, BARM. It is approximately 10 meters away from the National High Way. The school is composed of 63 teaching forces with 600 officially enrolled students for the School Year 2021-2022. This chosen school is the oldest and one of the top-performing schools in the Division of Maguindanao 1 and under K-12 Curriculum.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire, and test items for the pre-test and post-test were used to collect data. Survey questionnaires were employed and distributed to students and teachers who had responded to SOPs 1 and 5. Test items were used to measure the students' pre-test and post-test in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) for SOP number 2. The mean gain scores in Pre-test and Post-test were used for both the ALMs Group and the ADMs Group by calculating the arithmetic mean and standard deviation for SOPs 3 and 4. The T-test was used to determine the significant difference in Pre-test and Post-test mean scores, as well as the mean gain scores of the two experimental groups. The significance level for all tests was set at 0.05.

Procedure

The validation of the Research Instrument was the first priority before the conduct of the study. After which, the researcher asked permission to the District Supervisor and Principal of Dapiawan Central Elementary School to conduct the study.

After identifying the respondents of the study and securing all necessary approval for the conduct of such, the researcher followed a systematic way of gathering. The Pre-test was administered to both ALMs Group and ADMs Group with proper observance of the basic health protocol set by Inter-Agencies Task Force (IATF).

After the Pre-test, it is then that the treatment, which is the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) in teaching science was administered. The lessons that were presented to both groups were the same. Each lesson was comprised

of five stages of learning namely: Activity (Do), where the students will do the given learning activity to motivate them in the lesson being presented; Analysis (Think), where the students critically analyze the question being asked; Abstraction (Learn), where the lessons are being focused on the development of the concepts; and Application (Apply), in which activities were provided to assess students learning.

At the end of the class session, a Post-test was administered. The researcher himself was the one who conducted the pre-test and post-test to minimize threats to the instrument validity. Treatment effects were appraised based on mean gain scores. The content of the post-test was the same as that with the Pre-test.

Data Analysis

Using appropriate statistical tools, the data from the questionnaire survey was tallied, tabulated, and analyzed.

Part I. Mean and standard deviation was used to examine the data on the teacher's teaching performances in using ALMs and ADMs rated by students, peers, and the heads.

Part II. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data from the students' Pre-test and Post-test scores in using ALMs and ADMs.

For the third and fourth questionnaire, on the problems encountered by the teacher and students' perceptions under the ALMs and ADMs, mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the gathered data.

Results and Discussion

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher Under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) as Rated by Head

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under adaptive learning materials (ALMs) as rated by head are presented on Table 1.

Table 1. *Teaching performance of the DepEd Science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) as rated by head (n=5)*

	Statement	Mean	Description
	The science teacher:		
1	attends class everyday.	3.80	Always
2	uses class time efficiently.	4.00	Always
3	gives Adaptive Learning Materials regularly.	4.00	Always
4	releases Adaptive Learning Materials on time.	4.00	Always
5	gives reasons when Adaptive Learning Materials is not available to distribute on the given time.	3.40	Often
6	gives ample time to answer students queries on Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.80	Always
7	designs lesson plan to achieve the identified objectives in Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.80	Always
8	answer well the questions of the students.	4.00	Always
9	makes himself available to students for completion of activities.	3.40	Often
10	provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth.	4.00	Always
11	demonstrates efforts to stimulate student interest.	4.00	Always
12	utilizes instructional tools such as hand-outs and modules.	4.00	Always
13	emphasizes critical thinking and the "why" in the topics being presented.	4.00	Always
14	presents lessons in Adaptive Learning Materials in an orderly manner.	3.20	Often
15	presents lessons clearly in Adaptive Learning Materials with practical application in daily life.	3.80	Always
16	covers satisfactorily the content of the course	4.00	Always
17	gives illustrations in Adaptive Learning Materials that makes lesson clear.	4.00	Always
18	returns Adaptive Learning Materials activities regularly after correcting.	4.00	Always
19	encourages active participation of the students' in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	4.00	Always
20	uses different activities in Adaptive Learning Materialsto make lesson clear	4.00	Always
21	provides clear verbal instruction.	3.60	Always
22	observes protocols in giving Adaptive Learning Material	3.60	Always
23	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.40	Often
24	communicates clearly and accurately.	4.00	Always
25	listens attentively to the parents' concerns.	4.00	Always
26	checks activities regularly.	3.80	Always
27	conduct relevant course content.	3.80	Always
28	maintains recording of student's performances.	4.00	Always
29	is fair in giving grades.	4.00	Always
30	motivates me to admire the dedication of this teachers to his/her job.	4.00	Always
	Over-all Mean	3.847	Always

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or 26 out of 30 - item statements are rated by the school heads as “Always”. These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Materials. These are indicated by the item means in the range of 3.60–4.00.

The most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are: (a) statements number 2, 3, 4, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 24, 25, 28, 29, and 30 which says “Uses class time efficiently”, “Gives Adaptive Learning Materials regularly”, “Releases Adaptive Learning Materials on time”, “Answers well the questions of the students”, “Provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth”, “Demonstrates efforts to stimulate student interest”, “Utilizes instructional tools such as hand-outs and modules”, “Emphasizes critical thinking and the “why” in the topics being presented”, “Covers satisfactorily the content of the course”, “Gives illustrations in Adaptive Learning Materials that makes lesson clear”, “Returns Adaptive Learning Materials activities regularly after correcting”, “Encourages active participation of the students in using Adaptive Learning Materials”, “Uses different activities in Adaptive Learning Materials to make lesson clear”, “Communicates clearly and accurately”, “Listens attentively to the parents’ concerns”, “Maintains recording of student performances”, “Is fair in giving grades”, and “Motivates me to admire the dedication of this teachers to his/her job”(mean = 4.00; Description = Always)

On the other hand, 4 out of 30 - item statements are rated by the school heads as “Often”. This is indicated by the item means in the range of 3.20 - 3.40. These statements are: (a) statements number 5, 9, and 23 which says “Gives reasons when Adaptive Learning Materials is not available to distribute on the given time”, “Makes himself available to students for completion of activities” and “Motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Adaptive Learning Materials” (mean = 3.40; Description = Often); and (b) statement number 14 “Presents lessons in Adaptive Learning Materials in an orderly manner” (mean = 3.20; Description = Often).

The overall mean rating of the 30 items - statements of the teachers’ performances rated by the school heads are perceived to be “Always” as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.85. With this result, the use of Adaptive Learning Materials in teaching science subject is effective in enhancing teachers’ performances as it was shown on the feedback of the school head.

The result suggested that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials in teaching science subject has a positive effect in the teachers’ performances. This allows teachers to facilitate students accurately which anchored to their preferred learning.

Facilitation can be considered as a common term. Hence, the description of adaptive learning environments can be summarized as facilitating the learning process of each individual with appropriate learning conditions. Learning environment is complex structure that includes many students who has different characteristics. Students are physically and mentally different, so do their preferences. Thus, adaptation to these differences in educational environment is a necessity and adaptive learning materials facilitate in achieving this (Nguen and Do, 2008).

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as Rated by School Heads.

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under Alternative delivery mode (ADMs) as rated by peer are presented on Table 2.

Table 2. *Teaching performance of the DepEd science teacher using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as rated by school head (n=5)*

	Statement	Mean	Description
	The science teacher:		
1	attends class everyday.	3.80	Always
2	uses class time efficiently.	4.00	Always
3	gives Alternative Delivery Mode regularly.	3.80	Always
4	releases Alternative Delivery Mode on time.	4.00	Always
5	gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode is not available to distribute on the given time.	3.40	Often
6	gives ample time to answer students queries on Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.60	Always
7	designs lesson plan to achieve the identified objectives in Alternative Delivery Mode.	4.00	Always
8	answers well the questions of the students	4.00	Always
9	makes herself available to students for completion of activities.	3.40	Often
10	provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth.	3.20	Often
12	utilizes instructional tools such as hand-outs and modules.	4.00	Always
13	emphasizes critical thinking and the “why” in the topics being presented.	3.20	Often
14	presents lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode in an orderly manner.	3.40	Often
15	presents lessons clearly in Alternative Delivery Mode with practical application in daily life.	3.60	Always
16	covers satisfactorily the content of the course.	3.60	Always
17	gives illustrations in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear.	4.00	Always
18	returns Alternative Delivery Mode activities regularly after correcting.	4.00	Always
19	encourages active participation of the student’s in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.80	Always
20	uses different activities in Alternative Delivery Mode to make lesson clear.	4.00	Always
21	provides clear verbal instructions.	3.80	Always
22	observes protocols in giving Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.60	Always
23	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.40	Always
24	communicates clearly and accurately.	4.00	Always

25	listens attentively to the parents' concerns.	4.00	Always
26	checks activities regularly.	4.00	Always
27	conduct relevant course content.	3.80	Always
28	maintains recording of students' performances.	3.00	Often
29	is fair in giving grades.	3.00	Often
30	motivates me to admire the dedication of this teachers to his/her job.	3.00	Often
Over-all Mean		3.680	Always

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or 22 out of 30 - item statements are rated by the school heads as "Always". These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Alternative Delivery Modes (ADMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 3.40 – 4.00.

The most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are: (a) statements number 2, 4, 7, 8, 11, 12, 17, 18, 20, 24, 25 and 26 which says "Uses class time efficiently", "Releases Alternative Delivery Mode on time", "Designs lesson plan to achieve the identified objectives in Alternative Delivery Mode", "Answers well the questions of the students", "Demonstrate efforts to stimulate student interest", "Utilizes instructional tools such as hand-outs and modules", "Gives illustrations in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear", "Returns Alternative Delivery Mode activities regularly after correcting", "Uses different activities in Alternative Delivery Mode to make lesson clear", "Communicates clearly and accurately", "Listens attentively to the parents' concerns" and "Checks activities regularly" (mean = 4.00; Description = Always).

On the other hand, 8 out of 30 - item statements are rated by the school heads as "Often". This is indicated by the item means in the range of 3.00 - 3.40. These statements are: (a) statements number 5, 9 and 14 which says "Gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode is not available to distributed on the given time", "Makes herself available to students for completion of activities" and "Presents lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode in an orderly manner" (mean = 3.40; Description = Often); (b) statements number 10 and 13 which says "Provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth" and "Emphasizes critical thinking and the "why" in the topics being presented" (mean = 3.20; Description = Often); and (c) statements number 28, 29 and 30 which says "Maintains recording of students' performance", "Is fair in giving grades" and "Motivates me to admire the dedication of this teachers to his/her job" (mean = 3.00; Description = Often).

The overall mean rating of the 30 items - statements of the teachers' performances rated by the school heads are perceived to be "Always" as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.68. With this result, the use of Alternative Delivery Mode in teaching science subject can enhance teachers' performances. Alternative Delivery Mode of instruction makes teachers to be creative as it uses alternative ways of dealing student's needs. Thus, Teachers can employ several techniques to make the teaching process be effective and the learners could easily understand the subject matter being represented. Teachers must be knowledgeable of alternative approaches of teaching which will help every student learn everything in every way (Tullo, 2000).

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher Under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) as Rated by Peer

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under adaptive learning materials (ALMs) as rated by peer are presented on Table 3

Table 3. Teaching performance of the DepEd science teacher under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) as rated by peer (n=30)

	Statement	Mean	Description
	The science teacher:		
1	attends class regularly.	3.70	Always
2	comes to class on time.	3.30	Often
3	gives Adaptive Learning Materials regularly.	3.60	Always
4	releases Adaptive Learning Materials on time.	3.37	Often
5	gives reasons when Adaptive Learning Materials are not available to distribute on the given time.	3.50	Always
6	gives ample time to answer students queries on Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.57	Always
7	answers well the questions of the student.	3.37	Always
8	makes himself available to students for completion activities.	3.50	Always
9	provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth.	3.70	Always
10	emphasizes critical thinking and the "why" in the topics being presented.	3.33	Often
11	presents lessons in Adaptive Learning Materials in an orderly manner.	3.67	Always
12	presents lessons clearly in Adaptive Learning Materials with practical application in daily life.	3.47	Often
13	covers satisfactorily the content of the course.	3.40	Often
14	gives illustrations or samples in Adaptive Learning Materials that makes lesson clear.	3.63	Always
15	returns Adaptive Learning Materials activities regularly after correcting.	3.50	Always
16	encourages active participation of the students' in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.67	Always
17	uses different activities in Adaptive Learning Materials to make lesson clear.	3.43	Often
18	observes protocols in giving Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.63	Always

19	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.47	Always
20	shows approachability.	3.60	Always
21	listens attentively to the parents' concerns.	3.77	Always
22	checks activities regularly.	3.73	Always
23	shows amiable behavior.	3.50	Always
24	is fair in giving grades.	3.87	Always
25	motivates me to advise my students to learn from him/her.	3.67	Always
Over-all Mean		3.56	Always

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or nineteen out of 25 - item statements are rated by peers as “Always”. These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 3.37 - 3.87.

The top 5 most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are: (a) statement number 24 “Is fair in giving grades” (mean = 3.87; Description = always); (b) statement number 21 “Listens attentively to the parents’ concerns” (mean = 3.77; Description = Always); (c) statement number 22 “Checks activities.” (mean = 3.73; Description = Always); (d) statements number 1 and 9 which says “Attends class regularly” and “Provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth.” (mean = 3.70; Description = Always); and (e) statements number 11, 16 and 25 which says “Presents lessons in Adaptive Learning Materials in an orderly manner”, “Encourages active participation of the students in using Adaptive Learning Materials.” and “Motivates me to advise my students to learn from this teacher “(mean = 3.67; Description = Always).

On the other hand, six out of 25 - item statements are rated by peers as “Often”. This is indicated by the item means in the range of 3.30 - 3.47. These statements are: (a) statement number 12 “Presents lessons clearly in Adaptive Learning Materials with practical application in daily life.” (mean = 3.47; Description = Often); (b) statement number 17 “Uses different activities in Adaptive Learning Materials to make lesson clear” (mean = 3.43; Description = Always); (c) statement number 13 “Covers satisfactorily the content of the course” (mean = 3.40; Description = Often); (d) statement number 4 “Releases Adaptive Learning Materials on time” (mean = 3.37; Description = Often); (e) statement number 10 “Emphasizes critical thinking and the “why” in the topics being presented” (mean = 3.67; Description = Often); and (f) statement number 2 “Comes to class on time” (mean = 3.30; Description = Often).

The overall mean rating of the 25 items - statements of the teachers’ performances rated by peers are perceived to be “Always” as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.56. With this result, the use of Adaptive Learning Materials in teaching science subject can enhance teachers’ performances. The result suggested that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials in teaching science subject give positive effect in the teachers’ performances. This allows teachers to perform well as it was shown in the observed performances in teaching-learning process. Teachers in Adaptive Learning Materials observed adaptive collaboration as it supports involvement of social interaction between multiple persons in adaptive learning environment (Parmyrthis and Loidl Reisinger, 2004).

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher Under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as Rated by Peer

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as rated by peer are presented on Table 4.

Table 4. *Teaching performance of the DepEd science teachers under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as rated by peer (n=30)*

	Statement	Mean	Description
	The science teacher:		
1	attends class regularly.	3.80	Always
2	comes to class on time.	3.63	Always
3	gives Alternative Delivery Mode regularly.	3.53	Always
4	releases Alternative Delivery Mode on time.	3.43	Often
5	gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode are not available to distribute on the given time.	3.37	Often
6	gives ample time to answer students queries on Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.47	Often
7	answers well the questions of the student.	3.17	Often
8	makes himself available to students for completion of activities.	3.60	Always
9	provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth.	3.40	Often
10	emphasizes critical thinking and the “why” in the topics being presented.	3.03	Often
11	presents lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode in an orderly manner.	3.50	Always
12	presents lessons clearly in Alternative Delivery Mode with practical application in daily life.	3.30	Often
13	covers satisfactorily the content of the course.	3.27	Often
14	gives illustrations or samples in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear.	3.37	Often
15	returns Alternative Delivery Mode activities regularly after correcting.	3.53	Always
16	encourages active participation of the students’ in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.53	Always
17	uses different activities in Alternative Delivery Mode to make lesson clear.	3.17	Often
18	observes protocols in giving Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.43	Often

19	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.23	Often
20	shows approachability.	3.30	Often
21	listens attentively to the parents' concerns.	3.40	Often
22	checks activities regularly.	3.60	Always
23	shows amiable behavior.	3.37	Often
24	is fair in giving grades.	3.57	Always
25	motivates me to advise my student to learn from him/her.	3.50	Always
Over-all Mean		3.4	Often

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or fifteen out of 25 - item statements are rated by peers as “Often”. These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 3.03 - 3.47.

The top 3 most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are: (a) statement number 1 “Attends class regularly” (mean = 3.80; Description = always); (b) statement number 2 “Comes to class on time” (mean = 3.63; Description = Always); and (c) statements number 8 and 22 “Makes himself available to students for completion of activities” and “Checks activities” (mean = 3.60; Description = Always).

On the other hand, 15 out of 25 - item statements are rated by the peers as “Often”. This is indicated by the item means in the range of 3.03 - 3.47. These statements are: (a) statement number 6 “Gives ample time to answer students queries on Alternative Delivery Mode” (mean = 3.47; Description = Often); (b) statements number 4 and 18 “Releases alternative delivery mode on time” and “Observes protocols in giving Alternative Delivery Mode” (mean = 3.43; Description = Often); (c) statements number 9 and 21 “Provides opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth” and “Listens attentively to the parents' concerns” (mean = 3.40; Description = Often); (d) statements number 5, 14 and 23 “Gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode are not available to distribute on the given time”, “Gives illustrations in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear” and “Shows amiable behavior” (mean = 3.37; Description = Often); and (e) statements number 12 and 20 “Presents lessons clearly in Alternative Delivery Mode with practical application in daily life.” and “Shows approachability” (mean = 3.30; Description = Often).

The overall mean rating of the 25 items - statements of the teachers' performances rated by the peers are perceived to be “Often” as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.42. With this result, the use of Alternative Delivery Mode in teaching science subject is effective and can enhance teachers' performances.

The result reveals that the use of Alternative Delivery Mode in teaching science subject brings good effect in the teachers' performances. This allows teachers to perform well as it was shown in the observed performances in teaching-learning process. Also, this Alternative Delivery Mode help teacher to determine which teaching methods are appropriate to the students by assessing the type of learners. Furthermore, teaching methods work effectively mainly if they suit learners' needs since every learner interprets and responds to questions in a unique way (Chang, 2010). As such, alignment of teaching methods with students' needs and preferred learning influence students' academic attainments (Zeeb, 2004).

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher Under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) as Rated by Students

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under Adaptive Learning Material (ALMs) as rated by students are presented on Table 5.

Table 5. Ratings obtained in teaching performance of the DepEd science teacher under Adaptive Learning Material (ALMs) as rated by students (n=30)

	Statement	Mean	Description
The science teacher:			
1	gives Adaptive Learning Materials regularly.	3.53	Always
2	releases Adaptive Learning Materials on time.	3.57	Always
3	gives reasons when Adaptive Learning Materials are not available to distribute on the given time.	2.50	Often
4	gives ample time to answer students queries on ALMs	3.57	Always
5	answers well the questions of the student.	3.57	Always
6	presents lessons in ALMs in an orderly manner.	3.57	Always
7	presents lessons clearly in Adaptive Learning Materials with practical application in daily life.	3.53	Always
8	covers satisfactorily the content of the course.	3.27	Often
9	gives illustrations in ALMs that makes lesson clear.	3.50	Always
10	returns ALMs activities regularly after correcting.	3.43	Often
11	encourages active participation of the students' in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.67	Always
12	uses different activities in ALMs to make lesson clear.	3.77	Always
13	observes protocols in giving Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.40	Often
14	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the ALMs	3.87	Always
15	shows approachability.	3.27	Often
16	listens attentively to the parents' concerns.	3.50	Always

17	checks activities regularly.	3.50	Always
18	delivers effective learning to me.	3.80	Always
19	is fair in giving grades.	3.70	Always
20	motivates me to advise my friend to learn from him/her.	3.80	Always
Over-all Mean		3.51	Always

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or fifteen out of 20 - item statements are rated by students as “Always”. These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Material (ALMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 2.50 - 3.87.

The top 5 most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Adaptive Learning Material (ALMs) are: (a) statement number 14 “Motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Adaptive Learning Materials” (mean = 3.87; Description = Always); (b) statements number 18 and 20 “Delivers effective learning to me” and “Motivates me to advise my friend to learn from him/her” (mean = 3.80; Description = Always); (c) statement number 12 “Uses different activities in Adaptive Learning Materials to make lesson clear” (mean = 3.77; Description = Always); (d) statement number 19 “Is fair in giving grades” (mean = 3.70; Description = Always); and (e) statement number 11 “Encourages active participation of the students in using Adaptive Learning Materials” (mean = 3.67; Description = Always). These ratings coincide with what the researcher had observed from the teacher during the conduct of the study.

On the other hand, five out of 20 - item statements are rated by the students as “Often”. This is indicated by the item means in the range of 2.50 - 3.43. These statements are: (a) statement number 10 “Returns Adaptive Learning Materials activities regularly after correcting” (mean = 3.43; Description = Often); (b) statement number 13 “Observes protocols in giving Adaptive Learning Materials” (mean = 3.40; Description = Often); (c) statements number 8 and 15 “Covers satisfactorily the content of the course” and “Shows approachability” (mean = 3.27; Description = Often); and (d) statement number 3 “Gives reasons when Adaptive Learning Materials are not available to distribute on the given time” (mean = 2.50; Description = Often). The teaching performances shown are observed based on how the teachers do his/her job in delivering the adaptive learning materials.

The results tell us that the 20 items - statements of the teachers’ performances rated by students are perceived to be “Always” as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.51. With this result, the performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Material in teaching and learning process is effective among the Grade 6 students. This implies that teachers perform well in using the Adaptive Learning Materials as it was shown in the observed performances. Teachers in Adaptive Learning Materials observed adaptive collaboration; thus, the goal of the adaptive collaboration support is to form a group by taking the characteristics of different students into consideration (Brusilovsky, 1999 and Mödritscher, Garcia-Barrios, and Gütl, 2004).

Performance Ratings of the DepEd Science Teacher Under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as Rated by Students

The performance ratings of the DepEd science teacher under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as rated by students are presented on Table 6.

Table 6. Ratings obtained in teaching performance of the DepEd science teachers under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) as rated by students (n=30)

	Statement	Mean	Description
The science teacher:			
1	gives Alternative Delivery Mode regularly.	3.57	Always
2	releases Alternative Delivery Mode on time.	3.70	Always
3	gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode are not available to distribute on the given time	3.70	Always
4	gives ample time to answer students queries on Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.63	Always
5	answers well the questions of the student.	3.53	Always
6	presents lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode in an orderly manner.	3.80	Always
7	presents lessons clearly in Alternative Delivery Mode with practical application in daily life.	3.53	Always
8	covers satisfactorily the content of the course.	3.70	Always
9	gives illustrations in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear.	3.57	Always
10	returns ADMs activities regularly after correcting.	3.53	Always
11	encourages active participation of the students’ in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.57	Always
12	uses different activities in Alternative Delivery Mode to make lesson clear.	3.60	Always
13	observes protocols in giving Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.53	Always
14	motivates students to analyze the lesson in the Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.63	Always
15	shows approachability.	3.57	Always
16	listens attentively to the parents’ concerns.	3.42	Always
17	checks activities regularly.	3.63	Always
18	delivers effective learning to me.	3.57	Always
19	is fair in giving grades.	3.70	Always
20	motivates me to advise my friend to learn from him/her.	3.57	Always
Over-all Mean		3.60	Always

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

The data shows that all of the item statements or 20 out of 20 - item statements are rated by the respondents as “Always”. These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 3.42 - 3.80.

The top 5 most observed performances of the DepEd science teacher in the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are: (a) statement number 6 “Presents lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode in an orderly manner” (mean = 3.80; Description = Always); (b) statements number 2, 3, 8 and 19 which says “Releases Alternative Delivery Mode on time”, “Gives reasons when Alternative Delivery Mode are not available to distribute on the given time”, “Covers satisfactorily the content of the coarse ” and “Is fair in giving grades” (mean = 3.70; Description = Always); (c) statements number 4, 14, and 17 which says “Gives ample time to answer students queries on Alternative Delivery Mode”, “Motivates students to analyze the lesson in the alternative delivery mode” and “Checks activities regularly” (mean = 3.63; Description = Always); (d) statement number 12 “Uses different activities in Alternative Delivery Mode to make lesson clear” (mean = 3.60; Description = Always); and (e) statements number 1, 9, 11, 15, 18 and 20 which says “Gives Alternative Delivery Mode regularly”, “Gives illustrations in Alternative Delivery Mode that makes lesson clear”, “Encourages active participation of the students in using alternative delivery mode”, “Shows approachability”, “Delivers effective learning to me” and “Motivates me to advise my friend to learn from him/her” (mean = 3.57; Description = Always).

The results tell us that the 20 items - statements of the teachers’ performances rated by the students are perceived to be “Always” as proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.60. With this result, the performance of the DepEd science teachers in using Alternative Delivery Mode in teaching and learning process is effective among the Grade 6 students. This depicts that teachers perform well in using the Alternative Delivery Mode as it was shown in the observed performances. Further, the role of instructional materials in teaching and learning, commented that science education programmed cannot be taught effectively without the existence of equipment for teaching (Balogun, 1982).

Level of Pre-Test and Post-Test of ALMs Group

Table 7 presents the mean percentage scores of science students under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) in Pre-Test and Post-Test.

Table 7. *The pre-test and post-test scores of the science students under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) (n=30)*

Score	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Description
	F	%	F	%	
17 – 20	0	0	4	13.33	Excellent
13 – 16	0	0	17	56.67	Very Satisfactory
9 – 12	30	100.00	9	30.00	Satisfactory
5 – 8	0	0.00	0	0.00	Poor
0 – 4	0	0	0	0.00	Needs Improvement
Total	30	100	30	100	
Mean	9.4			14.43	
s.d.	0.62	(Satisfactory)		2.08	(Very Satisfactory)

The 30 selected students obtained the scores in the range of 9 – 12 in the pre-test. This score range is described as the average level of intelligent or a satisfactory performance in learning simple machines.

Majority of the post-test scores of the students under the ALMs group obtained the score range of 13 - 16 which is described as “Very Satisfactory”. This implies that students have the higher level of performance in simple machines. It also reveals that 9 or 30% of the respondents obtained the score range of 9 - 12 which is described as “Satisfactory” depicting that some students got a high level of performance in simple machines.

Moreover, 4 out of 30 students or 13.33% obtained the scores in the range of 17 - 20 described as excellent implying that there are few students who obtained the highest level of performance in simple machines.

The mean of the pre-test is 9.4 described as “Satisfactory”, interpreted that generally, the students have the high level of performance in simple machines with SD of 0.62, while the mean of the post-test was 14.43 described as “Very Satisfactory” interpreted as the students have a higher level of performance in simple machines with SD of 2.08. The mean of the Adaptive Learning Materials group increased at 1.22 from pre-test to post-test.

The result implies that most of the students are good when there is a learning material utilized by their teacher like Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) which was designed by the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education to the Bangsamoro learner.

This finding was in support of Erukoha and Umoren (2004) who affirmed that instructional materials facilitate learning of abstract concepts by helping to concretized ideas and stimulate learners’ imagination. Moreover, instructional materials help to increase active participation in the learning process.

Level of Pre-Test and Post-Test of ADMs Group

Table 8 present the mean percentage scores of science students under the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) in Pre-Test and Post-Test.

Table 8. *The pre-test and post-test scores of the science students under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) (n=30)*

Score	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Description
	F	%	F	%	
17 – 20	0	0	4	13.33	Excellent
13 – 16	0	0	17	56.67	Very Satisfactory
9 – 12	30	100.00	9	30.00	Satisfactory
5 – 8	0	0.00	0	0.00	Poor
0 – 4	0	0	0	0.00	Needs Improvement
Total	30	100	30	100	
Mean	9.53	(Satisfactory)	13.83	(Very Satisfactory)	
s.d.	0.78		2.08		

The 30 selected students obtained the scores in the range of 9 – 12 in the pre-test. This score range is described as the average level of intelligent or a satisfactory performance in learning simple machines.

On the other hand, majority of the students or 17 out of 30 students obtained the scores in the range of 13 - 16 and described as ‘Very Satisfactory’ or interpreted as students have the higher level of performance in simple machines. It also revealed that 9 out 30 students obtained the score range of 9 - 12 which implies that students have high performance level in simple machines.

Moreover, 4 out of 30 students obtained the scores in the range of 17 – 20, described as “Excellent”, or interpreted as students have the highest level of performance in simple machines. The mean of the pre-test is 9.53 with SD of 0.78 and the mean of post-test is 13.83 with SD of 2.00. The mean gain of 1.22 point was observed in the mean scores between the pre-test and post-test of the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) group.

This result is supported by the study conducted by Mathew (2012) which states that the use of instructional materials makes teaching effective as it enables learners to participate actively in classroom instruction. This view suggests that the use of instructional materials in teaching-learning can improve students’ performance.

Mean Gain Scores of ALM Group and ADM Group

The t-test analysis on the significant difference of the mean gain scores of the Adaptive Learning Materials group and Alternative Delivery Mode group is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. *The t-test analysis between the post-test scores of Adaptive Learning Materials group and Alternative Delivery Mode group (n=60)*

Group	N	Mean Score		Mean Gain	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular Value	Interpretation
		Pretest	Post test					
ALM Group	30	9.34	14.43	5.09	58	3.0899	1.672	Significant
s.d.		0.62	2.08	1.99				
ADM Group	30	9.5	13.08	3.58				
s.d.		0.82	2.00	1.79				

t-value > 1.672 to be significant at 0.05 level of significance

The data revealed that there is a significant difference since the computed t-value of 3.0899 is greater than the tabular value of 1.672 at 0.05 level of significance with df=58. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the mean gain scores between the students under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) is rejected. This implies that the students’ performances under ALMs group (Mean Gain = 5.09) is better than ADM group (Mean Gain = 3.58).

The result suggested that when the use of Adaptive Learning Materials is being contextualized or localized based on the students’ need, higher learning is possible. In fact, Garin et. al., (2016) stated that using contextualization to the academic performances of the diverse learners is an effective teaching learning strategy. Additionally, they recommended developing authentic, contextualized and localized instructional materials to improve the academic performance of learners.

Difference Between the Teachers’ Performances Under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM)

Shown in the Table 10 is the t- test result between the difference of the teachers’ performances under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM).

Table 10. The t-test analysis between the teachers' performance in ALMs and ADMs groups (n=130)

Rater	Paired Variable	N	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Tabular	Interpretation
Head Teacher	ALM	30	3.847	0.2330	58	2.188*	1.672	Significant
	ADM		3.680	0.3467				
Peer	ALM	20	3.557	0.1474	38	2.716*	1.685	Significant
	ADM		3.420	0.1708				
Students	ALM	25	3.515	0.2895	48	-1.407	1.687	Not Significant
	ADM		3.600	0.086				

t-value > tabular value to be significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship in the teachers' performance in Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) Groups as rated by the head teachers (t-value 2.18) and peers (t-value 2.72). The t-value of each rater are greater than the tabular value. Therefore, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the performances between the teachers under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM)" is rejected.

On the other hand, the students as a rater with t-value of -1.41 is smaller than the tabular value implying that Ho2 is accepted, Therefore the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the performances between the teachers under the Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM)" is accepted.

Problems Encountered by Science Teacher Under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs)

The problems encountered by the science teacher under adaptive learning materials (ALMs) are presented on Table 11.

Table 11. Problems encountered by science teachers under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) (n=30)

	Statement	Mean	Description
1	I found this Adaptive Learning Materials not useful to my teaching.	3.27	Agree
2	I feel stressed in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.53	Strongly Agree
3	I cannot cope with the lessons in Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.27	Agree
4	I am worried of the performance of my student in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.33	Agree
5	I am pressured in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.40	Agree
6	I am confused of the learning of my student in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.43	Agree
7	I am stressed in producing Adaptive Learning Materials because it consumes my time.	3.40	Agree
8	The content of the materials are not suit enough for the learning of my student.	3.43	Agree
9	I am not sure of the reliability of the students' answer	3.10	Agree
10	I don't see any good in using Adaptive Learning Materials.	3.43	Agree
	Over-all Mean	3.36	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

Majority or nine out of 10 - item statements are described by the respondents as "Agree". These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 310 - 343.

On the same table, the top three problems encountered by the respondents under Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are: (a) statement number 2 "I feel stressed in using adaptive learning materials" (mean = 3.53; Description = Strongly Agree); (b) statements number 8 and 10 "The content of the materials are not suit enough for the learning of my students" and "I don't see any good in using adaptive learning materials" (mean = 3.43; Description = Agree); and (c) statements number 5 and 7 "I am pressured in using adaptive learning materials" and "I am stressed in producing adaptive learning materials because it consumes my time" (mean = 3.40; Description = Agree).

In general, the overall mean is 3.36 which is "Agree". It indicates that teachers are having difficulty in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) in teaching. The teachers feel stressed and pressured in using the materials it is because the content of the materials is not suited enough to the learning of the students. This forces the teacher to contextualize the content of the materials in order for the students to adapt in the learning process.

Contextualized teaching and learning approach as a teaching approach is underutilized because it can give additional workload to the teachers to modify the curriculum. The system-wide implementation of contextualized teaching is relatively nonexistent because preparations of the modified content, instructional materials and instructional approach have to be made. So, mechanizing classroom practices is becoming more prevalent (Ambrose et al. 2013).

Problems Encountered by Science Teacher Under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM)

The problems encountered by the science teacher under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) are presented on Table 12.

The data shows that all of the respondents described the 10 - item statement as "Agree" These statements reflect the observed performance of the DepEd science teacher in using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM). These are indicated by the item means in the range of 277 - 320.

Table 12. *Problems encountered by science teachers under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) (n=30)*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	I found this Alternative Delivery Mode not useful to my teaching.	3.07	Agree
2	I feel stressed in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	2.97	Agree
3	I cannot cope with the lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.07	Agree
4	I am worried of the performance of my student in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	2.90	Agree
5	I am pressured in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.20	Agree
6	I am confused of the learning of my student in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	3.00	Agree
7	I am stressed in producing Alternative Delivery Mode because it consumes my time.	2.90	Agree
8	The content of the materials are not suit enough for the learning of my student.	2.77	Agree
9	I am not sure of the reliability of the students answer.	3.03	Agree
10	I don't see any good in using Alternative Delivery Mode.	2.99	Agree
	Over-all Mean	3.07	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

On the same table, the top three problems encountered by the respondents under Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are: (a) statement number 5 “I am pressured in using Alternative Delivery Mode “(Mean = 3.20; Description = Agree); (b) statements number 1 and 3 which says “I found this Alternative Delivery Mode not useful to my teaching” and “I cannot cope with the lessons in Alternative Delivery Mode” (Mean = 3.07; Description = agree); and (c) statement number 9 “I am not sure of the reliability of the students answer.” (Mean = 3.03; Description = Agree).

In general, the overall mean is 3.07 which is “Agree”. It indicates that teachers are having difficulty in using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) in teaching. It is because they feel pressured in using the Alternative Delivery Mode, they find it not useful to their teaching because of the high standard set by the national in the content of the materials. Furthermore, some of the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) content are so high which gives difficulty for the teacher to cope up with the lessons. Moreover, because of the high standard content concern in the Alternative Delivery Mode the teachers are having doubt about the reliability of the student’s answers.

This finding contradicted the study about the alternative delivery mode of instruction which claimed that it can be an option for teachers in schools to answer the needs of accessing quality basic education depending on the situation (Alternative Delivery Mode, 2012).

Perceptions of Students Towards the Use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs)

The perceptions of students towards the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are presented on Table 13.

Table 13. *Perceptions of students towards the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) (n=30)*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) makes learning more fun.	3.70	Strongly Agree
2	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) helps me understand basic concepts in science.	3.53	Strongly Agree
3	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) explains concepts well.	2.80	Strongly Agree
4	I can follow Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) instruction easily.	3.57	Strongly Agree
5	The contents of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) are suited enough for my learning.	3.33	Agree
6	I find Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) integration makes learning science easier.	3.70	Strongly Agree
7	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) provides Substantial learning.	3.67	Strongly Agree
8	I like Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) because it requires critical, logical thinking and deep analysis.	3.53	Strongly Agree
9	I consider Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) relevant in learning science.	3.57	Strongly Agree
10	I like having Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) in learning science because they are relevant to my needs.	3.43	Strongly Agree
11	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) motivate me to learn science subject.	3.63	Strongly Agree
12	I feel more confident in getting higher scores on this Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs).	3.53	Strongly Agree
13	I am convinced that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can help to increase my performance in science subject	3.23	Agree
14	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) encourage me to answer all the given task/activity.	3.37	Agree
15	I am satisfied to the content of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs).	3.37	Agree
16	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) makes significant contribution in learning science.	3.60	Strongly Agree
17	I like the subject because the knowledge and skills derived can be applied in daily life.	3.47	Agree
18	I consider Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) necessary in learning science subject.	3.57	Strongly Agree
19	Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) helps me more in the learning progress.	3.50	Strongly Agree
20	I advise my friend to use Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) on their study.	3.50	Strongly Agree
	Over-all Mean	3.48	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

The data revealed the perception of students in using Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs). The table shows the result of students’ responses with corresponding standard deviation and description. The overall mean of students’ response is 3.48 which mean most of the students “Strongly Agree” that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can enhance students’ performances in learning

science. Statement 1 “Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) makes learning more fun” and statement 6 “I find Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) integration makes learning science easier” both have the highest mean and with a strongly agree description. Statements 1 and 6 with a mean of 3.70 have the highest mean. This implies that most of the students “Strongly Agree” that they were motivated and they enjoyed in learning science by the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs)

On the other hand, statement 13 “I am convinced that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can help to increase my performance in science subject” have the lowest mean and with an agree description. Statement 13 obtained a mean of 3.23 which means that most of the students “Agree” and convince that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can help to increase their performance in learning science subject.

The data above clearly states that the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) brings impact in enhancing the students’ performances in learning science subject. This means that the students strongly agree that learning science subject with Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can enhance students’ performances. Further, Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) helps and motivates students to overcome their learning needs.

This finding is affirmed by Dr. Serhart Kurt, (2021) who found out that students’ reported learning is higher if the content was taught using adaptive learning. They experienced less stress due to adaptive pace, as students must be ready to move on before new concepts are introduced.

Similarly, the modular learning resources hopes to engage the learners into guided and independent learning activities at their own pace and time. Furthermore, this aims to help learners acquire the needed 21st century skills while taking into consideration their need and circumstances (ALMs, 2020).

Perception of Students Towards the Use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs)

The perceptions of students towards the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are presented on Table 14.

Table 14. *Perceptions of Students Towards the Use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) (n=30)*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) makes learning more fun.	3.40	Agree
2	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) helps me understand basic concepts in science.	3.40	Agree
3	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) explains concepts well.	3.57	Strongly Agree
4	I can follow Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) instruction easily.	3.37	Agree
5	The contents of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are suited enough for my learning.	3.20	Agree
6	I find Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) integration makes learning science easier.	3.47	Agree
7	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) provides substantial learning.	3.37	Agree
9	I consider Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) relevant in learning science.	3.43	Agree
10	I like having Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) in learning science because they are relevant to my needs.	3.57	Strongly Agree
11	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) motivates me to learn science subject.	3.50	Strongly Agree
12	I feel more confident in getting higher scores on this Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs).	3.30	Agree
13	I am convinced that the use of Alternative learning materials (ADMs) can help to increase my performance in science subject.	3.40	Agree
14	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) encourages me to answer all the given task/activity.	3.43	Agree
15	I am satisfied to the content of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs).	3.50	Strongly Agree
16	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) makes significant contribution in learning science.	3.23	Agree
17	I like the subject because the knowledge and skills derived can be applied in daily life.	3.67	Strongly Agree
18	I consider Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) necessary In learning science subject.	3.37	Agree
19	Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) helps me more in the learning progress	3.47	Agree
20	I advise my friend to use Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) on their study.	3.47	Agree
Over-all Mean		3.425	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.59, Often; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.49, Never

The data shows the perception of students in using Adaptive Learning Materials. The table shows the result of students’ responses with corresponding standard deviation and description. The overall mean of students’ response is 3.425 which mean most of the students “Agree” that the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are good and can enhance students’ performances in learning science. Statement number 17 “I like the subject because the knowledge and skills derived can be applied in daily life” have the highest mean with a “Strongly Agree” description. Statement number 17 with a mean of 3.67 has the highest mean, depicting that most of the students “Strongly Agree” that students like the subject because the knowledge and skills derived can be applied on their daily life.

On the other hand, statement 5 “The contents of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are suited enough for my learning” have the lowest mean and with an “Agree” description. Statement 5 obtained a mean of 3.20 revealing that most of the students agree that the contents of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) are suited enough in learning science subject.

The data above clearly states that the use of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) has a positive impact in enhancing the students’

performances in learning science subject. This means that the students agree that learning science using Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) can enhance students' performances. Furthermore, Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) helps students to understand the concept in science meaningfully which create a concrete idea that will not be easily forgotten.

Moreover, with this given learning experience, the instructional material help the students develop their self-esteem, communication skills, critical thinking and peer relations as they undergo collaborative works. Further, it increased the students' understanding and knowledge of the science concepts (Kirk, 2015).

Alternative Delivery Mode of instruction was introduced in order to address the learning needs of the marginalized students (Department of Education, 2011; Philippines ADMs Evaluation Philippines, 2012).

Conclusions

According to the findings, the use of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Mode (ADMs) in teaching is effective, as proven by the observed performances of DepEd science teachers as rated by their head teachers, peers, and students. Teachers in the ALMs group, on the other hand, did slightly better than the ADMs group. The respondents have a comparable learning performance in science after taking all essential tests such as pre-test, post-test, and survey questionnaire. According to the t-test, the ALMs Group performed somewhat better than the ADMs Group in learning the topic in science 6 after being exposed to Adaptive Learning Materials for ALMs and Alternative Delivery Mode for ADMs.

Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) have a significant impact on students' learning performance. According to the results of the survey the majority of them "Strongly Agree" that learning science subjects with Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) can improve students' performance. As a result, in this time of pandemic, the use of Adaptive Learning Materials in learning science, particularly simple machines, is beneficial. Furthermore, ALMs undergo content contextualization for students to cope with the lesson, based on the adaption of the region, particularly the student's skills.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher arrived at the following recommendations:

Because the efficacy of these materials has been proven in this study, school administration should encourage all teachers to adopt Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) in their teaching.

Science teachers are urged to employ Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) in their classrooms at all grade levels to help students struggling with science concepts.

The findings revealed that using Adaptive Learning Materials and Alternative Delivery Mode in the classroom can improve both teacher and student performance. However, when these two materials (ALMs and ADMs) in the teaching-learning process are compared, it is recommended that the usage of adaptive learning materials be maintained and improved in order to obtain better results in teaching and learning.

The teacher should continue to provide time for students to contextualize the contents so that they can cope with the session at their own speed and needs.

Future researchers will do similar research with different courses and themes to learn more about the usage of Adaptive Learning Materials (ALMs) and Alternative Delivery Modes (ADMs) in teaching and learning sciences.

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